

Tubular Lap Joints in Composite Cylindrical Shells under External Bending and Shear

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ABSTRACT

The problem of a tubular adhesive lap joint between two concentric cylindrical shells of dissimilar materials and thicknesses is considered. The loadings are of non-axisymmetric type and they are applied as an external bending moment and a shear force away from the joint. By taking the loads, shell stress resultants, and displacements, and adhesive layer stresses as multiples of either $\cos\theta$ or $\sin\theta$, it is possible to calculate stresses due to the external bending moment and shear loads transmitted through the joint. The analysis and solution procedure is applied to a sample problem. The numerical results of this nonsymmetric loading are compared with those of the axisymmetric loading by tension and by torsion.

INTRODUCTION

Multi-layer advanced composite tubes and cylindrical shells are being used in diverse areas in technology as primary and secondary structural elements (1). These advanced systems are, in general, an assemblage of thin, anisotropic, concentric, circular cylindrical shells of dissimilar materials bonded or joined through thin adhesive layers. Thus, current highly developed adhesive bonding or joining techniques provide a method of assembling high-strength and lightweight structural systems. In many cases these tubes are required to carry bending moment and shear loads. Usual configurations for tubular adhesive joints employed in practice are shown in Fig. 1a and b. Although, the joints shown in Fig. 1 are between one inner and one outer cylindrical shell, this is not always so. In some cases, the inner or outer shell (or both) may themselves consist of several layers.

In engineering and scientific literature, there seems to be very few papers concerning the analysis of tubular adhesive joints. One of the early analytical studies on axisymmetric tubular lap joint under external tension and torsion loading was conducted by Lubkin and Reissner (2). They presented a closed form solution based on elastic, isotropic, axisymmetric cylindrical shell theory. They assumed the thicknesses and materials of the inner and outer shells are identical. Volkersen (3) presented another solution based on similar simplifications. A solution making use of finite element technique and which agrees with the numerical results of Lubkin and Reissner (2) is presented in (4). However, the adhesive layer stresses obtained by finite elements near the edges in (4)

Fig. 1. Tubular Joints: (a) Tubular Lap Joint, (b) Sleeve Joint

are different from those of (2).

More recently, the present authors (5,6) analyzed the general tubular lap joints between dissimilar, anisotropic cylindrical shells subjected to uniaxial tension and torsion. This solution (5,6) is based on a higher order anisotropic shell theory including the effect of transverse shear deformations in the shells.

The main objective of this paper is to extend the previous study to the case of cylindrical shell (or tubular) lap joints composed of shell elements of different material characteristics and thicknesses and subjected to the external bending moment and shear loadings of Fig. 2. The previous study by the present authors (5,6) treated the problem of the tubular lap joint under uniaxial tension and torsion loading (Fig. 2a), which are axisymmetric problems. In contrast, the problem considered in this paper is one of nonsymmetric loading corresponding to the loadings shown in Fig. 2 b,c.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Each tube or shell is treated as an orthotropic elastic shell undergoing extensional, bending, in-plane shear, twisting, and transverse shear deformations. The principal orthotropic material directions are assumed to coincide with the principal directions of shell curvature. The resultants of the normal stresses in each shell are related to the extensions and curvature changes by

Fig. 2. Loading on Tubular Lap Joint: (a) Tension and Torsion, (b) Shear, (c) Bending Moment.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_\theta \\ M_x \\ M_\theta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & B_{11} & B_{12} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & B_{12} & B_{22} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & D_{11} & D_{12} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & D_{12} & D_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_\theta \\ K_x \\ K_\theta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The shear stress resultants and displacement variables are related as follows:

$$Q_x = C_1(\beta_x + \partial w / \partial x) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_\theta = C_2(\partial w / \partial \theta - v) / R \quad (3)$$

$$N_{x\theta} = N_{\theta x} = A_{66}[\partial v / \partial x + (1/R)\partial u / \partial \theta] + B_{66}[\partial \beta_\theta / \partial x + (1/R)\partial \beta_x / \partial \theta] \quad (4)$$

$$M_x = M_x = B_{66}[\partial v / \partial x + (1/R)\partial u / \partial \theta] + D_{66}[\partial \beta_\theta / \partial x + (1/R)\partial \beta_x / \partial \theta] \quad (5)$$

In addition to the shell stress-strain relations given in Eqs. (1)-(5), the shell generalized stresses must satisfy the equilibrium equations of cylindrical shells. Also, the extensions ϵ_x and ϵ_θ and curvatures K_x and K_θ are related to the displacements u , v , w , β_x , and β_θ .

As shown in Fig. 1, over the length of the adhesive joint, let superscripts 1 and 2 refer to the inner and outer shells, respectively. The cylindrical shell generalized stress, strain, and displacement variables $N_x^1, N_\theta^1, M_x^1, M_\theta^1, Q_x^1, \epsilon_x^1, \epsilon_\theta^1, K_x^1, K_\theta^1, u^1, w^1$, and β_x^1 vary in the circumferential direction as multiples of $\cos\theta$. The variables $N_{x\theta}^1, N_{\theta x}^1, M_{x\theta}^1, M_{\theta x}^1, Q_\theta^1, v^1$, and β_θ^1 vary as multiples of $\sin\theta$. Thus, mathematically

$$N_x^i = \bar{N}_x^i \cos \theta, N_\theta^i = \bar{N}_\theta^i \cos \theta, \dots \quad (6)$$

and

$$N_{x\theta}^i = \bar{N}_{x\theta}^i \sin \theta, M_{x\theta}^i = \bar{M}_{x\theta}^i \sin \theta, \dots \quad (7)$$

Similarly, the adhesive layer stresses satisfy

$$\sigma_z = \bar{\sigma}_z \cos \theta, \tau_{zx} = \bar{\tau}_{zx} \cos \theta, \tau_{z\theta} = \bar{\tau}_{z\theta} \sin \theta \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_z = B \epsilon_z, \tau_{zx} = G_x \gamma_{zx}, \tau_{z\theta} = G_\theta \gamma_{z\theta} \quad (9)$$

Then, the mechanical behavior of the adhesive layer or the coupling between the inner and outer shells is expressed as

$$\sigma_z = B(w^2 - w^1)/t \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{zx} = G_x(u^2 + z^2 \beta_x^2 - u^1 - z^1 \beta_x^1)/t \quad (11)$$

$$\tau_{z\theta} = G_\theta(v^2 + z^2 \beta_\theta^2 - v^1 - z^1 \beta_\theta^1)/t \quad (12)$$

where B , G_x , and G_θ are elastic constants of the adhesive and t is the adhesive layer thickness.

After some algebraic manipulations, the equilibrium and strain displacement equations reduce to a matrix differential equation in the form

$$\frac{d}{dx} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\bar{Y}^1(x)\} \\ \{\bar{Y}^2(x)\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}^{11} & \bar{A}^{12} \\ \bar{A}^{21} & \bar{A}^{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\bar{Y}^1(x)\} \\ \{\bar{Y}^2(x)\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

The column matrices $\{\bar{Y}^i(x)\}$ are each of order 1×10 and consist of the following elements:

$$\{\bar{Y}^i(x)\} = \{\bar{N}_x^i, \bar{U}^i, \bar{M}_x^i, \bar{\beta}_x^i, \bar{Q}_x^i, \bar{w}^i, \bar{N}_{x\theta}^i, \bar{v}^i, \bar{M}_{x\theta}^i, \bar{\beta}_\theta^i\} \quad (14)$$

($i = 1, 2$)

The matrices $[\bar{A}^{ij}]$ are the matrices corresponding to material and geometric constants. Boundary conditions and continuity or matching conditions for portions of the structure are expressed in terms of elements of the matrices $\{\bar{Y}^i(x)\}$ evaluated at the appropriate values of x .

The differential equation Eq. (13) is to be solved with appropriate boundary and matching conditions corresponding to the external non-axisymmetric bending and shear loading cases given in Fig. 2b,c, respectively. An efficient numerical scheme for solving two-point boundary value problems of the type given by Eq. (13) is discussed in (5,6,7). After the elements of $\{\bar{Y}^1(x)\}$ and $\{\bar{Y}^2(x)\}$ in Eq. (14) are obtained from the solution of Eq. (13) then the adhesive layer stresses are computed by substituting needed displacement and angle of rotation quantities in Eqs. (10)-(12).

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The analytical procedure developed is applied to a sample problem of a tubular lap joint under external bending and shear. For the sake of simplicity, in the numerical calculations, the inner and outer tubes are assumed to be of similar isotropic material and identical thicknesses. Also, an average shell radius R is assumed. It should be noted, though, that the analysis presented here is valid for any tubular lap joint with two dissimilar, orthotropic cylindrical shell elements.

For the sample problems the geometric ratios are:

Fig. 3. Distribution of Bond Stresses for External Bending Moment Loading

Fig. 4. Distribution of Bond Stresses for External Tension Loading

$$R/h = 20, \quad \ell/R = 0.25, \quad t/h = 0.02.$$

The elastic constant ratios are: $G_x/E = G_\theta/E = 0.001$, $B/E = 0.002$, $\nu = 0.333$ where B , G_x , G_θ are elastic constants of the adhesive and E is the Young's modulus of the shell layers and ν is the Poisson's ratio.

For the numerical results the adhesive stress quantities $\bar{\sigma}_z$, $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$, $\bar{\tau}_{\theta z}$ are normalized with respect to the nominal stresses in the tubes away from the joint region. These nominal stresses are defined as follows:

$$\text{Bending moment loading: } \sigma_m = M_0/\pi R^2 h \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Axial tension loading: } \sigma_n = N_0/2\pi R h \quad (18)$$

$$\text{Shear loading: } \tau_q = Q_0/\pi R h \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Torsional loading: } \tau_t = T_0/2\pi R^2 h \quad (20)$$

The stress distributions in the adhesive layer along the length of the joint in terms of nondimensionalized adhesive stresses are plotted in Figs. 3-6. The plots for axisymmetric loading cases in Fig. 4 and 6 are also included here for the purposes of comparison with those of the external bending and shear loadings of Fig. 3 and 5. For instance, note the order of magnitude similarity in stresses between Figs. 3 and 4 and also between Figs. 5 and 6.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

For the tubular lap joint under bending moment loading (Fig. 3) the dominant adhesive layer stresses are the normal stress $\bar{\sigma}_z$ and the longitudinal shear stress $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$. The circumferential shear stress $\bar{\tau}_{\theta z}$ is much smaller in magnitude and may be treated as negligible in practical applications. The peak values of these stresses occur at the edges of the bond region, which are locations of geometric and material discontinuity.

A simple comparison of the plots of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 indicate that the adhesive stresses in both cases are of the same order of magnitude and have similar trends. Therefore, it can be concluded that, on the basis of the similarity of the stress distributions, the axisymmetric case of uniaxial tension load N_0 might be used for a quick estimate the adhesive stress distribution in the non-axisymmetric case of external moment loading M_0 . This is due to the fact that, in the bending moment case, adhesive stresses change much more slowly in the circumferential direction than the longitudinal direction.

In the case of a tubular lap joint subjected to external shear loading (Fig. 5), the dominant adhesive layer stress is the circumferential shear stress $\bar{\tau}_{\theta z}$, whereas the stresses $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_z$ are practically zero.

The non-axisymmetric loading case of Fig. 5 can be compared with the axisymmetric case of Fig. 6. The magnitude of and the trend in the stresses in both cases are nearly similar. Thus, at least for the short length tubular joints, the axisymmetric case of uniaxial torsion loading may be used for an order of magnitude estimate of adhesive maximum stresses corresponding to the non-axisymmetric external shear loading case. For long joints, this result may not be valid, because the bending moment component of the external shear loading Q_0 may significantly increase the values of $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_z$.

In passing, it should be observed here that, contrary to the theory of elasticity, the shear stresses $\bar{\tau}_{xz}$ do not vanish at the edges of the joint in all axisymmetric as well as non-axisymmetric external loading cases. This fact is a natural consequence of modeling the adhesive layer as a continuous compression-tension and shear springs instead of a continuum (8).

Fig. 5. Distribution of Bond Stresses for External Shear Loading

Fig. 6. Distribution of Bond Stresses for External Torsion Loading

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